

INTEGRATIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING MUSIC EDUCATION AND ITS ANALYSIS

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Abstract: This article examines the issues of modern music education in the text of integration processes, synthesizes the experience of applying the principles of complex, systematic and interdisciplinary approaches to the main stages of formation of XX musical education. It is intended for the further development and experimental introduction of high and middle level pedagogues to the pedagogical process; ideas are presented as educational material in music pedagogy courses and special methods.

Keywords: Integrative education, music culture, integrativism, educational trends, scientific activity, master classes.

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At the current stage of the development of music pedagogy, it is becoming more and more important to bring the complex and uncertain processes of updating and reorganizing the content of the existing system of training and education of musicians to the most optimal solution. Today's level of musical education requires a scientific analysis and generalization of the possibilities of experimental directions in educational work describing the creative and scientific-research activities of teachers of various music institutions. This task is important after the uneven development of individual aspects and links of educational and musical-pedagogical systems in various specific historical situations and the need for their coordination and coordination. The most advanced and scientifically-based way to change the system of training musicians in order to more closely connect the educational process with real practical activity is not only a highly qualified performer, but also theoretically qualified and practically trained music teachers. is the integration of educational content that allows education.

Discussion:

The researches of leading scientists are devoted to the problems of quality training of teachers in the field of music education: including European and Russian experts B. L. Yavorsky, L. A. Barenboym, A. D. Alekseeva and others. The idea of integration appeared at the bottom of politics and economy, it is used in the most clear and noble sense. At the same time, it is one of the most promising and advanced methods of solving problems in the modern world community. Integration is a process that leads to the emergence of a number of common features, new features of different elements.

Integration processes have created similar problems in front of music and pedagogy. They are not only performing musicians, but also musicians who are able to raise music pedagogy to a new level, who are able to introduce new ideas in teaching. 'the teacher includes the tendency to provide full training of musicians.

Scholars give an excellent definition of music education, which is still relevant today: "only artists should teach, not teachers with voices".

In fact, there is a significant gap between the development of advanced pedagogic science and the actual methodological level of the wide practice of teaching at primary and secondary levels - music schools and music colleges. The reason for this is the inconsistency of the level of readiness of music graduates of higher education for pedagogical activity, often focused only on performance, not on teaching. A paradox arises: on the one hand, a highly literate, intellectually developed musician appears above the level of higher education, whose views, assessment criteria, close to the ideal of the performance repertoire, knowledge of the goals and tasks of his pedagogical work, on the other hand, when he comes to work, he faces specific individual problems when working with students, feels unprepared to solve many tasks, and as a result loses confidence in himself as a teacher and turns his creative needs into executive, rarely in cases - the choirmaster tries to direct his activities. There are many new methodological developments in local and world pedagogy that help update the content of music education, and in everyday life, approaches that are increasingly ineffective and inappropriate in terms of today's requirements are still a problem. The idea of integrating educational content is very suitable for the tasks of temporary pedagogy. When we talk about the fundamentalization of music teacher training, the inclusion of meaningful and reasonable connections in its context, we have the task of solving the problems of the music teacher's personality formation. According to some researchers, "the process of integration is a unifying process based on the development of relationships between elements aimed at effective achievement of goals. This process is related to the formation of a whole system and strengthening of its unity" [2, p. 157].

Integration in the field of music education is a phenomenon in which the experience during work activities includes scientific and practical work experience. The closest integration is the idea of a comprehensive approach to education, its goal is to connect various components of education and upbringing, to introduce various complex courses into the curriculum, interdisciplinary research and practical developments, close to the main specialty. connection with science and others. In the process of development and implementation, the integrated approach to education has achieved positive results in a number of universities, in the work of leading teachers in the past, but it has never become a holistic educational system. The disadvantage of the development of these ideas is that the main goal of this method was to connect different components of musical education, but the specific characteristics of the connections and the elements they combine were not defined. The experience of developing and implementing the complex method had its positive and negative sides, which undoubtedly influenced the passing of these ideas into the background, their insignificance at the current stage of the development of musical education. Nevertheless, the generalization of the experience of the leading teachers of the past, related to the most advanced idea of the integrated approach to education and training, will help to restore the overview of the state of music education and a new promising way of its development. , which is reflected in the interdisciplinary approach that is being actively implemented today.

Integrative process in the process of musical education The idea of educating not only a music performer, but also a music teacher has ancient roots in the history of music education. In the first conservatories founded by the brothers Anton and Nikolai Rubinstein, great attention was paid to the pedagogical direction and the requirements for its level were quite

high. The seriousness of the attitude to ensure the content of the professional training of a music teacher is fully practice-oriented is confirmed by the duration of education.

In pre-school educational institutions and schools, general musical education is actually considered as an organization that carries out the main work activity in the process of training pedagogic personnel, and lessons are organized accordingly.

Profiling of music teachers of the 20th century, which still exists today (training of personnel for music schools and art schools), turned out to be limited to the minimum knowledge and skills acquired by students in the complex of the general musical pedagogical direction. The situation became more acute when the departments and faculties of music education and instructor pedagogy in higher education were terminated. There is a clear inconsistency between the internationally recognized highest level of local music art and education and the unsatisfactory state of daily life of peripheral music educational institutions, which is due to the low quality of the work of trained musicians-teachers in such conditions and related to efficiency.

A gradual revival of scientific-pedagogical thought and social activity in the field of musical education was observed. So far, this task has not been fully solved. He identified a number of promising directions:

- implementing the principles of a systematic approach to the content and organization of music teacher training;
- integration of special performance, musical-theoretical and psychological-pedagogical sciences.

The conceptual characteristics of the necessary professional training of music teachers as specialist personalities are determined by qualified pedagogues as follows:

- to strengthen the humanitarian component of education of the future music teacher;
- aesthetic general artistic direction of all aspects of preparation for musical and pedagogical activity;
- deepening of basic psychological and pedagogical knowledge;
- establishing the professional basis of music teacher training;
- attention to socio-cultural and professional reality before practical activity;
- mastering promising methodologies and active methods of musical education;
- philosophy of musical education;
- information in the training of a modern music teacher.

New concepts have appeared in modern pedagogy: "integrativism", "integrative approach", objective factors that help to introduce the ideas of integration into the wide practice of pedagogical activity are analyzed, the importance of parts, their characteristics are determined, which makes them organic with other parts allows to combine. Increasingly, scientists are raising the issue of technological support for the integration process in pedagogy.

A. Ya. Daniluk rightly notes that the saturation of science with more and more knowledge of various origins makes it a task to adopt effective countermeasures that allow to provide a synthetic perception of this knowledge:

- practical problems in the educational process;
- solving scientific and theoretical problems;
- extensive use of cybernetic machines in the educational process;

➤ active use at all stages of education methods that ensure the instillation of skills for independent learning [3].

Pedagogical process, according to the opinion of leading qualified teachers, involves the development of the experience of education itself, the use of various forms of lessons (individual, individual group, open lessons, master classes, concert and pedagogical practice, etc.), theoretical and should be directed to the analysis of practical training. It is also important to consider the psychological and pedagogical issues of promoting professional musical activity.

Issues of educational integration N. A. Gorelik believes that the task of forming the personal structure of students is possible only in the conditions of combining all their activities [5].

The task of developing the ability of modern students not only to acquire knowledge, but also to integrate knowledge remains the most urgent in the era of rapid development of information technologies. In the field of musical creative skills, the integration of knowledge in the field of information technology is very relevant, it encourages students to develop creative abilities, forms the need for personal and creative self-awareness. T. L. Likhacheva, from a theoretical point of view, integration "is understood not only as a connection between individual elements of the system, but also as an organic set based on their interpenetration and unity. can provide a sustainable impetus to increase educational results to the first level in terms of reducing costs and increasing the quality of results" [4, p. 62].

Summary

In conclusion, it should be noted that in accordance with today's trends, there is a need to search for a pedagogical model of integration, to rely on new principles of teaching, the need to take them into account requires time. The research of leading scientists in the field of pedagogical activity indicates the search for different ways to solve this problem. Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- modern research in this field is based on the significant experience of previous scientific developments based on the ideas of interdisciplinary and complex relations;
- scientific research examines both general theoretical problems of integration and integration of scientific knowledge in various fields of science and applied sciences;
- there was a need to study the entire spectrum of musical education problems in each specific musical specialty, based on the achievements of modern pedagogic science.

In our opinion, this should begin not with solving practical problems such as partial changes in curricula and programs, but with a clear definition of the goals and objectives presented for higher education today.

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